

Determinants of physical activity in wheelchair users with spinal cord injury and lower limb amputation

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to gain insight into determinants of physical activity behaviour of wheelchair users with spinal cord injury or lower limb amputation, from the perspective of both wheelchair users and rehabilitation professionals. Seven focus groups were conducted: five with wheelchair users (n=25) and two with professionals (n=11). The transcripts were analysed using a sequential coding strategy, in which the reported determinants of physical activity were categorized using the physical activity for people with a disability model. Reported personal determinants of physical activity were age, general health status, stage of life, demotivation due to difficulty burning calories, available time and energy, balance in daily life, attitude, and history of a physically active lifestyle. Reported environmental determinants were professional guidance, inconvenient exercise times, accessibility of facilities, costs, transportation difficulties, equipment difficulties, and social support. Important, changeable determinants of physical activity that might be influenced in future lifestyle interventions for wheelchair users are: balance in daily life leading to more time and energy to exercise, attitude towards physical activity, professional guidance, accessibility of facilities (providing information on how and where to find accessible facilities), and social support (learning how to get this).

Keywords amputation, focus group, determinants, exercise, physical activity, spinal cord injury, wheelchair

Introduction

During inpatient rehabilitation, wheelchair users are encouraged to adopt a physically active lifestyle by working towards an active and independent existence as much as possible (van Langeveld, Post et al. 2011; van den Berg-Emons, Bussmann et al. 2008). However, in the time following inpatient rehabilitation, it is difficult for wheelchair users to maintain or further enhance their physical activity (van den Berg-Emons, Bussmann et al. 2008). In order to develop effective interventions to increase physical activity, it is valuable to know the determinants of a physically

active lifestyle in wheelchair users, from a behaviour change approach (Bartholomew, Parcel et al. 1998). Although several studies have been carried out in wheelchair users on determinants of physical activity behaviour, no single study contains the perspectives of both wheelchair users and rehabilitation professionals. Asking both wheelchair users and professionals which determinants are related to physical activity provides valuable insights on where interventions should focus on from both viewpoints. Moreover, the implementation of lifestyle interventions based on insights of both professionals and wheelchair users may be more feasible and effective (Morgan, Engsborg et al. 2017). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to gain insight into determinants of a physically active lifestyle, which should be taken into account in the development of an eHealth intervention targeting a physically active lifestyle in wheelchair users with spinal cord injury (SCI) or lower limb amputation.

Methods

Design

This research is part of the Wheelchair Exercise and Lifestyle Study (WHEELS) project. The main objective of this project is to develop a mobile application for wheelchair users with SCI or lower limb amputation to promote a healthy lifestyle in terms of physical activity behaviour, nutrition behaviour and relaxation behaviour. The study design was descriptive, using focus groups for qualitative data collection. The focus groups for wheelchair users and health care professionals were conducted separately.

Participants and setting

In June 2017, seven focus groups were performed. Three focus groups (two focus groups with wheelchair users and one with professionals) took place in the rehabilitation centre Reade and three (two focus groups with wheelchair users and one with professionals) took place in Heliomare. The final focus group took place in October 2017, during the annual meeting day of the Dutch Spinal Cord Injury Association in Ede, The Netherlands. A total of 25 wheelchair users and 11 rehabilitation professionals participated.

Procedures and interview guide

All focus groups took place in a conference room and lasted a maximum of 90 minutes. During the focus groups a semi-structured interview was held, guided by a moderator. The assistant moderator took notes to identify the respondents on the audio-recording transcription and to identify main themes. The research team decided to ask open questions regarding a healthy lifestyle, the questions in the interview guide were not specified towards activity behaviour, nutrition behaviour or relaxation behaviour. This to ensure that all participants could express what they considered most important regarding lifestyle. This abstract focuses on determinants of physical activity in wheelchair users, the results on nutrition and relaxation will be published elsewhere.

Data analysis

After the focus groups, the moderator and assistant-moderator evaluated and discussed the most notable emotions, statements and themes. The audio recordings were transcribed verbatim, after which they were coded. Three types of coding were used: open, axial and selective coding. The Physical Activity for people with a Disability (PAD) model was used to classify areas of determinants related to a healthy physical activity pattern (selective coding) (van der Ploeg, van der Beek et al. 2004). To ensure reliability of coding and data interpretation, the analyses were

carried out by two researchers (LEA and TD). Disagreements were discussed and in case of persisting disagreements, a third researcher was consulted (JFMH).

Results

Reported personal determinants of physical activity were age, general health status (e.g. physical overload of the arms, comorbidities, decubitus), stage of life, demotivation due to difficulty burning calories, available time and energy, balance in daily life, attitude towards physical activity, and history of a physically active lifestyle. Reported environmental determinants were professional guidance, inconvenient exercise times, accessibility of facilities, costs, transportation difficulties, equipment difficulties, and social support.

Conclusion and discussion

This research provides valuable insights for the development of physical activity interventions for wheelchair users with SCI or lower limb amputation. Determinants that might be influenced in future lifestyle interventions for wheelchair users are: balance in daily life leading to more time and energy to exercise, attitude towards physical activity, professional guidance, exercise times, accessibility of facilities (providing information on how and where to find accessible facilities), and social support (learning how to get this). Determinants that cannot be altered but are also important according to wheelchair users and rehabilitation professionals are: general health status, age, stage of life, and previous experiences with a physically active lifestyle. These determinants might be valuable when considering personalising of future lifestyle interventions.

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